

EFFECTS OF AGRICULTURAL EXTENSION TEACHING METHODS ON THE ADOPTION OF IMPROVED RICE PRODUCTION TECHNOLOGIES IN EKITI STATE, NIGERIA.

¹Aremu P. A. and ²Akinboye O. A.

¹National Cereal Research Institute, Badeggi, Niger State, Nigeria.

²Department of Agricultural Extension and Rural Development, Ladoke Akintola University of Technology, Ogbomoso

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Abstract: *The effectiveness of agricultural extension services is often hindered by traditional teaching methods that do not cater to the learning preferences of farmers. This study investigates the effects of agricultural extension teaching methods on the adoption of improved rice production technologies in Ekiti State, Nigeria. A multistage sampling technique was used in selecting 150 respondents for the study. Primary data were collected with the aid of a well-structured interview schedule. Descriptive statistical tools employed include; frequency counts, percentages, and weighted mean score (WMS) while Pearson product moment correlation (PPMC) was used to test the study hypothesis. The findings revealed that the rice farmers' mean age is 44 years, having an average household size of 4 person and 14 years as the mean number of years spent in formal school. The mean farm size of respondents is 2.9 hectares, with a mean annual income of #595,420. The finding further revealed that demonstration plots, farmer field schools (FFS), workshops and training sessions and peer learning and farmer-to-farmer extension were the utilized extension teaching methods for disseminating improved rice production technologies in the study area. Findings indicate a high level of effect of extension teaching methods on the adoption of improved rice production technologies. Increased yields, resource-use efficiency, enhanced quality of produce and pest and disease resistance were the benefits derived by the respondents in adopting improved rice production technologies. Also, economic constraints, knowledge and information gaps, inadequate infrastructure and cultural and social resistance were the constraints encountered by the respondents in adopting improved rice production technologies. Significant relationship exist between respondents' age, household size, years spent in formal school, years of experience in rice farming, size of rice farm and annual income and effects of agricultural extension teaching methods on the adoption of improved rice production technologies. In conclusion, the findings of this study underscore the effects of agricultural extension teaching methods on the adoption of improved rice production technologies among farmers. It was recommended that there should be the development of targeted training programs that cater to the specific needs of farmers, focusing on practical applications of improved rice*

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production technologies.

Background Information

Rice is the staple food for over half the world's population and the most important among all the cereal crops (Dogara and Jumare, 2014). Approximately 480 million metric tons of milled rice is produced annually. China and India alone account for 50% of the rice grown and consumed globally. In Nigeria rice has consumption per capita of 32 kg indicating 4.7% increase in the past decade making the total consumption to be 6.4 million tons in 2017 as against 3.7 million tons produced per year (Erhie, 2018; Mohammed, et al, 2019). Despite the increase in rice production, Nigeria can only meet 49 percent of its own internal demand (Udemezue, 2018). Therefore, to enhance rice production and improve food security, the dissemination of effective agricultural extension teaching methods is essential as agricultural extension services act as a bridge between agricultural researchers and farmers facilitating the transfer of agricultural technologies, knowledge and best practices to improve farm productivity and income. Agricultural extension services play a crucial role in disseminating knowledge and technologies to the farmers facilitating their adoption and implementation on the field. Agricultural extension services are pivotal in facilitating the transfer of knowledge and technology from research institutions to farmers, particularly in developing countries where agriculture forms the backbone of the economy and food security. It plays a crucial

role in enhancing agricultural productivity and improving the livelihoods of farmers. They serve as a bridge between research institutions and farmers, disseminating knowledge about new agricultural practices and technologies. One of the primary focuses of agricultural extension is to promote the adoption of improved agricultural technologies, such as those related to rice production, which is a staple food for over half of the world's population (Pingali, 2012). The need for extension services became very necessary in order to provide farmers with development information in order to solve widespread agricultural problems. Bonye, et. al., (2012) argued that extension provides a source of information on new technologies for farming communities which when adopted can improve production, incomes and standards of living. Extension service providers make an innovation known to farm households, act as a catalyst to speed up adoption rate and also control change and attempt to prevent some individuals in the system from discontinuing the diffusion process (Alemu, et. al., 2016). Extension teaching methods are devices, modes or channels used to create situations in which new information can pass freely from the source (extension worker or research institutes) to the farming communities (Ayanda, 2019). There are various extension teaching methods used as tools by the extension workers to effect desirable changes in the behaviour of farmers which include; group training, demonstration plot, adopted villages,

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On -Farm Adaptive Research and mass media (Nwaekpe, et. al., 2014). Agricultural extension is basically aimed at providing farmers with essential knowledge and skills that would assist them in taking vital decisions which would ultimately lead to increased production (Ephraim and Gloria, 2013). Extension agents therefore, will need to carefully adapt communication strategies and channels to effectively pass on the required message in each local situation. Effective communication between change agents and researchers is essential for increasing agricultural production through the use of improved technologies. Effective agricultural extension teaching methods are essential for promoting these technologies. Various approaches, including participatory learning, field demonstrations, and group training sessions, have been employed to enhance farmers' understanding and encourage the adoption of innovations (Davis et al., 2010). Research indicates that the choice of extension teaching methods significantly influences farmers' willingness and ability to adopt new practices as participatory methods that involve farmers in the learning process tend to be more effective than conventional top-down approaches (Adekunle et al., 2015). Additionally, the success of these teaching methods is not solely dependent on the content being taught but is also influenced by socio-economic factors, such as farmers' education levels, access to resources, and local agricultural practices (Khan et al., 2018). Studies have shown that when extension services consider these contextual factors, they

are more likely to achieve higher adoption rates of improved technologies (Feder et al., 1985). The effectiveness of agricultural extension services is often hindered by traditional teaching methods that do not cater to the learning preferences of farmers (Lee and Lichtenstein, 2016). Limited access to information and inadequate training has been identified as barriers to the adoption of improved rice production technologies (Kivlin and Lentz, 2017). Despite the development of improved rice production technologies such as high-yielding varieties, integrated pest management, and sustainable agronomic practices, adoption rates among smallholder farmers remain alarmingly low due to ineffective agricultural extension teaching methods which is often highlighted as a significant barrier (Pingali, 2012; Garside and Sutherland, 2013). Therefore, understanding how agricultural extension teaching methods influence the adoption of improved rice production technologies, ultimately aiding in the formulation of effective strategies to enhance agricultural productivity and food security. This research investigates the effects of agricultural extension teaching methods on the adoption of improved rice production technologies in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study describe the socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents, utilized extension teaching methods for disseminating improved rice production technologies, effects of agricultural extension teaching methods on the adoption of improved rice production technologies, level of effects of agricultural

extension teaching methods on the adoption of improved rice production technologies, benefits of adopting improved rice production technologies and constraints to adoption of improved rice production technologies. It was hypothesized that there is no significant relationship between the respondents' demographic characteristics and effects of agricultural extension teaching methods on the adoption of improved rice production technologies.

Methodology

The study was carried out in Ekiti State, Nigeria and is bounded to the north by Kwara State, to the northeast by Kogi State, to the south and southeast by Ondo State, and to the west by Osun State. The Yorubas make up the majority of the state's population. Ekiti State was formed from a part of old Ondo State in 1996 and has its capital as the city of Ado-Ekiti. One of the smallest states of Nigeria, Ekiti is the 31st largest in area and 30th most populous with an estimated population of 3.592 million as of 2022 (National Population Commission web, and National Bureau of Statistics web). The state is divided between the Nigerian lowland forests in most of the state and the drier Guinean forest–savannah mosaic in the north. Ekiti State is partially based around agriculture, mainly of yams, rice, cocoa, and cassava crops. The State is mainly an upland zone, rising over 250 meters above sea level. It lies on an area underlain by metamorphic rock. It is generally an undulating part of the country with a characteristic landscape that consists of old plains broken by step-sided out-crops that may

occur singularly or in groups or ridges. The State enjoys tropical climate with two distinct seasons. These are the rainy season (April–October) and the dry season (November–March). Temperature ranges between 21° and 28 °C with high humidity. The south westerly wind and the northeast trade winds blow in the rainy and dry (Harmattan) seasons respectively. Tropical forest exists in the south, while savannah occupies the northern peripheries. Ekiti State consists of sixteen Local Government Areas. They are: Ado-Ekiti, Ikere, Oye, Aiyekire (Gbonyin), Efon, Ekiti East, Ekiti South-West, Ekiti West, Emure, Idoosi, Ijero, Ikole, Ilejemeje, Irepodun/Ifelodun, Ise/Orun, Moba. A multistage sampling procedure was employed for the selection of rice farmers for this study in the study area. Ekiti State was divided into three (3) agricultural development programme (ADP) zones namely; Zone I, Zone II, and Zone III to facilitate agricultural extension services across the 16 local government areas. Zone I and II: Comprise five local government areas each while Zone III: Comprises six local government areas. Firstly, simple random sampling technique was used in selecting 2 zones namely Zone I and Zone III. Secondly, 3 blocks was selected from each of the three agricultural development programme zones making a total of three (6) blocks. The third stage involved a random selection of five (5) cells from each of the 6 blocks making a total of 30 cells. Lastly, a random selection of 5 rice farmers from each of the fifteen 30 cells making a total of one hundred and fifty (150) rice farmers that constituted the sample size for the study.

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Primary data was collected using a well-structured interview schedule. Data was analysed using descriptive and inferential statistical tools to test the stated hypothesis.

Results and discussion

Respondents' demographic characteristics

Results presented in Tables 1 revealed that 48% the rice farmers were between the age range of 40-49 years while 16.7% were between the age range of 50-59 years and 12% of them were between 30-39 years. Also, 17.3% are below 30 years of age and 6% were 60 years of age and above with a mean age of 44 years. This indicates that more than half of the respondents (60%) were within the mean age and were considered as been productive, economically active, able-bodied and agile young men and women who possessed the physical strength to sustain rigorous and arduous tasks required in rice farming. The study finding is in line with the reports of Nwofoke et al., (2024) that the mean age of the rice farmers was 44 but disagrees with the finding of Amusa et al., (2020) who reported that the mean age of the rice farmers was 48 years. Also, as presented in Table 1, 56% of the rice farmers had household size of less than 5 people while 20.7% of them had household size of between 5-6 people, 13.3% of them had household size of 7-8 people and 10% had household size of 9 people and above with the mean household size of 4 people. This implies that the respondents had small household size which indicates there that there would be unavailability of family labour to carryout farming activities. This finding is in

tandem with the report of Ruedas and Guico (2021) that the rice farmers had small-scale household size but in disagreement with the findings of Michael et al., (2024) that the mean household size was 7persons per household. The table further reveals that 46% of the rice farmers spent between 13-18 years in formal school while 18.7% of them spent between 1-6 years in formal school and 13.3% of the rice farmers spent between 7-12years in formal school. Also, 12% of them spent 19years and above in formal school while 10% of the rice farmers had no formal education. The mean number of years spent in formal school by the rice farmers was 14 years. The above finding implies that the rice farmers had relatively high level of formal education which could enhance their communication and comprehension of technical agricultural information. This finding is in disagreement with the report of Apuyor et al., (2023) that the rice farmers had low level of formal education which could be a barrier to the adoption of innovation that could have improved their production and productivity level. Likewise, the table shows that 10% of the rice farmers had less than 5 years of experience in rice farming, 64.7% had between 5-6 years of experience in rice farming while 9.3% of them had between 7-8 years of experience in rice farming and 16% of them had 9 years and above in rice farming experience with 5.2 years as the mean year of experience in rice farming. This indicates that the sampled rice farmers had less than 10 years of experience in rice farming which implies that they may have limited knowledge and understanding of rice

production technologies thus making it more challenging for them for them to grasp and effectively implement information provided through agricultural extension teaching methods and at the same time may be more resistant to change and less inclined to adopt new and improved technologies. Also, these farmers may lack practical experience in the implementation of new rice production technologies. The above finding is in line with the report of Michael et al., (2024) that most of the respondents had experience of less than 10 years with 4.4 years as the mean years of experience in the study area. Result presented in Table 1 further shows that 50% of the rice farmers cultivate less than 3ha of rice farm while 31.3% of them cultivate between 3-4ha of rice farm and 18.7% cultivate 5ha of rice farm and above with 2.9ha as the mean size of rice farm cultivated by the respondents. This indicates that the rice farmers in the study area cultivate less than 3ha of rice farm thus

operating on a small-scale which may be as a result of the respondents having limited financial resources thus making it more challenging for them to invest in new technologies. This finding corroborates the report of Alabi et al., (2023) that majority of the rice farmers in the study area were small holders. Table 1 shows that 34.7% of the rice farmers earned between #300,000- #499,999 annually and 39.3% earned an annual income of between #500,000-#699,999 while 14.7% earned #900,000 and above annually. Less than four percent (3.3%) earned below #300,000 annually with #595,420 as the mean annual income. The above finding indicates that rice farming in the study area is profitable. Higher mean annual income may indicate that the farmers have greater financial resources to invest in improved rice production technologies. This finding corroborates the report of Abdullahi et al., (2022) that rice production is highly profitable in the study area.

Table 1: Distribution of the respondents by demographic characteristics (n=150)

Respondents characteristics	Frequency	Percentage	Mean
Age(yrs)			
<30	26	17.3	
30-39	18	12	44years
40-49	72	48	
50-59	25	16.7	
60>	9	6	
Household size			
<5	84	56	
5-6	31	20.7	
7-8	20	13.3	4people
9>	15	10	
Years spent in formal school			

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0	15	10	
1-6years	28	18.7	
7-12years	20	13.3	14years
13-18years	69	46	
19years>	18	12	
Years of experience in rice farming			
<5	15	10	
5-6	97	64.7	5.2years
7-8	14	9.3	
9>	24	16	
Respondents' size of rice farm(Ha)			
<3	75	50	
3-4	47	31.3	2.9ha
5>	28	18.7	
Respondents' annual income			
<#300,000	5	3.3	
#300,000-#499,999	52	34.7	#595,420
#500,000-#699,999	59	39.3	
#700,000-#899,999	12	8	
#900,000>	22	14.7	

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Utilized extension teaching methods for disseminating improved rice production technologies

Result presented in Table 2 shows that demonstration plots ranked 1st with a weighted mean score of 2.71, farmer field schools (FFS) ranked 2nd with a weighted mean score of 2.68, workshops and training sessions ranked 3rd with a weighted mean score of 2.66 and peer learning and farmer-to-farmer extension ranked 4th with a weighted mean score of 2.65 were the utilized extension teaching methods for disseminating improved rice production technologies in the study area. Utilizing a combination of these extension teaching

methods can significantly enhance the adoption of improved rice production technologies and together they can create a comprehensive approach to farmer education and technology adoption. This indicates that demonstration plots serve as practical, hands-on learning environments where farmers can observe and compare traditional practices with improved technologies as they are particularly effective in showcasing the benefits of new varieties and practices. This implies that demonstration plots can lead to increased adoption rates of improved practices, as they provide tangible evidence of benefits as they foster peer learning which can stimulate interest among

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neighbouring farmers (Kafle and Poudel, 2018). Farmer field schools offer a participatory learning environment where farmers can engage in discussions, field observations, and practical decision-making as it is particularly useful for holistic understanding and sustainable practices. This implies that farmer field schools can significantly enhance farmers' knowledge, leading to increased confidence and adoption of improved practices as farmers develop critical thinking skills, which are essential for adapting to changing agricultural conditions (Van den Berg and Jiggins, 2007). Workshops and training sessions are structured educational opportunities that provide in-depth knowledge about specific technologies or practices as they are often led by experts and tailored to address the needs of farmers. This implies that workshops and training sessions can lead to significant knowledge transfer, resulting in higher adoption rates of improved practices.

They also create networks among farmers, fostering collaboration and peer support (Aker, 2011). Peer learning emphasizes the sharing of experiences and knowledge among farmers and particularly effective in communities where trust and relationships are strong. This implies that peer learning can enhance the adoption of practices as farmers are more likely to trust information from fellow farmers as it encourages a sense of community and collective growth (Poudel and Kafle, 2019). Also, farmer-to-farmer extension employs local farmers as extension agents who share knowledge and experiences with other farmers as it leverages local knowledge and cultural practices. This implies that this method can lead to higher adoption rates due to the relatability and credibility of local farmers as it fosters community engagement and can be more cost-effective compared to traditional extension services (Fadama, 2020).

Table 2: Distribution of the respondents by utilized extension teaching methods for disseminating improved rice production technologies (n=150)

Utilized extension teaching methods for disseminating improved rice production technologies	WMS	Rank
Demonstration plots	2.71	1 st
On-farm trials	2.52	9 th
Extension publications	2.56	8 th
Farmer field schools (FFS)	2.68	2 nd
Radio and television programmes	2.63	5 th
Mobile apps and digital platforms	2.61	6 th
Workshops and training sessions	2.66	3 rd
Advisory services	2.45	11 th
Networking and partnerships	2.48	10 th
Peer learning and farmer-to-farmer extension	2.65	4 th
Social Media Engagement	2.59	7 th

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WMS-Weighted mean score

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Effects of agricultural extension teaching methods on the adoption of improved rice production technologies

Table 3 shows that knowledge dissemination and enhanced skills ranked 1st with a weighted mean score of 2.48, skill development ranked 2nd with a weighted mean score of 2.47, peer learning and influence ranked 3rd with a weighted mean score of 2.45 and access to resources and information ranked 4th with a weighted mean score of 2.43 were the effects of agricultural extension teaching methods on the adoption of improved rice production technologies. Extension teaching methods play a vital role in enhancing knowledge dissemination, skill development, peer learning, influence, and access to resources, all of which significantly impact the adoption of improved rice production technologies thus, by employing a combination of these methods; extension services can foster greater agricultural innovation and productivity. This indicates that effective knowledge dissemination is critical in bridging the gap between research and practice as it facilitates the transfer of knowledge about improved rice practices. This implies that increased agricultural knowledge typically leads to higher adoption rates of improved technologies. Farmers who are well-informed are more likely to implement new practices, resulting in improved productivity and

sustainability (Aker and Mbiti, 2010). Skill development is crucial for the effective implementation of new technologies thus extension methods provide farmers with practical skills necessary for adopting improved rice production techniques. This implies that when farmers acquire new skills, they gain confidence in their ability to implement improved practices, leading to increased adoption rates (Sulaiman and Davis, 2012). Peer learning is a method where farmers learn from each other through shared experiences. This approach is often facilitated in community settings, such as farmer field schools and group workshops. This implies that peer learning enhances social cohesion and trust, which can lead to a greater willingness to adopt new technologies. Farmers are more likely to trust information shared by their peers, making this an effective method for promoting adoption (Poudel and Kafle, 2019). Influence refers to the impact of social networks and relationships on farmers' decisions to adopt improved technologies. Extension agents, community leaders, and early adopters play a significant role in influencing other farmers. This implies that when influential community members adopt new practices, they often serve as role models, encouraging others to follow suit. This can create a ripple effect, leading to widespread adoption of improved rice production

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technologies (Bandura, 2004). Access to resources, such as seeds, fertilizers, and financial assistance, is critical for the adoption of improved technologies. Extension teaching methods often provide information about available resources and how to access them.

This implies that when farmers have better access to resources and information, they are more likely to adopt improved practices. Extension services that facilitate access to these resources can significantly enhance agricultural productivity (Okwu and Nwankwo, 2019).

Table 3: Distribution of the respondents by effects of agricultural extension teaching methods on the adoption of improved rice production technologies (n=150)

Effects of agricultural extension teaching methods on the adoption of improved rice production technologies	WMS	Rank
Knowledge dissemination and enhanced skills	2.48	1 st
Increased awareness	2.41	5 th
Building trust and relationships	2.38	6 th
Feedback mechanisms	2.29	8 th
Peer learning and influence	2.45	3 rd
Behavioural change	2.26	9 th
Access to resources and information	2.43	4 th
Sustainability and long-term adoption	2.34	7 th
Skill development	2.47	2 nd

WMS-Weighted mean score

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Level of effects of agricultural extension teaching methods on the adoption of improved rice production technologies

Result presented in Table 4 shows that the level of effects of agricultural extension teaching methods on the adoption of improved rice production technologies is high (54.7%). The high level of effect of extension teaching methods on the adoption of improved rice production technologies is evident through increased knowledge, behavioural change, higher adoption rates, and community engagement which contribute to enhanced agricultural productivity, sustainability, economic empowerment, and resilience against

climate change. The high level of effect of extension teaching methods on the adoption of improved rice production technologies is a crucial factor in enhancing agricultural productivity, food security, and the livelihoods of farmers. The high level of effect of extension teaching methods on the adoption of improved rice production technologies indicates that extension teaching methods significantly improve farmers' understanding of new technologies and practices. This implies that improved adoption of technologies leads to higher yields, contributing to food security and economic growth (Aker and Mbiti, 2010). Also, the high level of effect of extension teaching

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methods on the adoption of improved rice production technologies indicates that the effectiveness of these methods is often reflected in the willingness of farmers to change their traditional practices in favour of improved technologies. This implies that employing robust extension services have higher rates of technology adoption compared to those without such services (Davis, 2008). The high level of effect of extension teaching methods on the adoption of improved rice production technologies further indicates that extension methods promote collective learning and

community involvement, leading to shared experiences and support among farmers. Effective extension methods often incorporate sustainable practices, leading to more efficient use of resources and reduced environmental impact. This implies that higher productivity and improved practices can lead to increased incomes for farmers, enhancing their overall quality of life (Rogers, 2003). Knowledge dissemination through extension can equip farmers with strategies to adapt to climate variability, improving their resilience (Sulaiman and Davis, 2012).

Table 4: Distribution of the respondents by level of effects of agricultural extension teaching methods on the adoption of improved rice production technologies

Level of effects of agricultural extension teaching methods	Frequency	Percentage
High	82	54.7
Moderate	51	34
Low	17	11.3
Total	150	100

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Benefits of adopting improved rice production technologies

Table 5 shows that increased yields ranked 1st with a weighted mean score of 2.15, resource-use efficiency ranked 2nd with a weighted mean score of 2.12, enhanced quality of produce ranked 3rd with a weighted mean score of 2.09 and pest and disease resistance ranked 4th with a weighted mean score of 2.08 were the benefits of adopting improved rice production technologies. Utilizing extension teaching methods to promote the adoption of improved rice production technologies can lead to several significant benefits, including increased yields, resource-use efficiency, enhanced quality of

produce, and improved pest and disease resistance. These benefits collectively contribute to better livelihoods for farmers and greater sustainability in agricultural practices. Increased yields indicate that extension teaching methods effectively convey knowledge about improved varieties and practices, leading to higher yields thus; farmers who adopt these practices often see substantial increases in productivity. This implies that higher yields contribute to increased food security and income for farmers, which can lead to improved livelihoods (Pingali, 2012). Resource-use efficiency indicates that extension methods focus on teaching sustainable practices and

efficient resource use, such as optimal fertilizer application, water management, and pest control techniques. These teachings can minimize waste and maximize output. This implies that improved resource-use efficiency leads to cost savings for farmers and can enhance environmental sustainability. Efficient use of inputs helps to reduce the ecological footprint of rice production (Cassman and Pingali, 1995). Similarly, enhanced quality of produce indicate that extension programs often educate farmers on best practices for improving the quality of their rice, including post-harvest handling, storage techniques, and varietal selection as this focus on quality can directly

influence marketability. This implies higher quality produce can lead to better market prices and increased competitiveness. This is vital for smallholder farmers aiming to access higher-value markets (Okello, 2010). Pest and disease resistance indicates that extension methods educate farmers on integrated pest management (IPM) and the use of disease-resistant rice varieties. This knowledge helps farmers proactively manage pests and diseases. This implies that improved pest and disease resistance leads to reduced crop losses and less reliance on chemical pesticides, promoting both economic and environmental sustainability (Alavi, 2012).

Table 5: Distribution of the respondents by benefits of adopting improved rice production technologies (n=150)

Benefits of adopting improved rice production technologies	WMS	Rank
Increased farmer knowledge and skills	2.05	5 th
Behavioural change and attitude shift	1.84	13 th
Enhanced access to resources	2.04	6 th
Increased yields	2.15	1 st
Strengthened community and peer support	1.76	15 th
Sustainability	1.90	11 th
Enhanced quality of produce	2.09	3 rd
Increased profitability	2.02	7 th
Climate resilience	1.87	12 th
Resource-use efficiency	2.12	2 nd
Reduced labour requirements	1.96	9 th
Better resource management	1.93	10 th
Market opportunities	1.99	8 th
Pest and disease resistance	2.08	4 th
Food security	1.81	14 th

WMS-Weighted mean score

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Constraints to adoption of improved rice production technologies

As shown in Table 6, economic constraints ranked 1st with a weighted mean score of 2.11, knowledge and information gaps ranked 2nd with a weighted mean score of 2.08, inadequate infrastructure ranked 3rd with a weighted mean score of 2.05 and cultural and social resistance ranked 4th with a weighted mean score of 2.03 were the constraints to adoption of improved rice production technologies. The adoption of improved rice production technologies can be significantly hindered by various constraints, including economic constraints, knowledge and information gaps, inadequate infrastructure, and cultural and social resistance. This indicates that economic constraints can deter farmers from adopting new technologies. Extension services may struggle to motivate farmers to invest in improved practices when financial viability is uncertain. This implies that high economic barriers can lead to low adoption rates, perpetuating cycles of poverty among farmers. Extension methods that do not address these constraints may be less effective in promoting adoption (Feder, 1985). The result further indicates that knowledge and

information gaps result into farmers often lacking access to relevant information about improved rice technologies and extension methods that fail to bridge these gaps will likely see limited success. This implies that knowledge gaps can lead to misconceptions about new technologies, reducing farmers' willingness to adopt them. Effective extension methods must ensure that accurate and timely information reaches farmers (Aker, 2011). Inadequate and poor infrastructure can limit farmers' ability to adopt improved practices. Extension services may be less effective if farmers cannot access necessary resources. This implies that inadequate infrastructure can lead to post-harvest losses and decreased market access, further discouraging the adoption of new technologies (World Bank, 2008). Cultural and social resistance can create resistance to adopting new technologies as farmers may prefer traditional practices while social dynamics can influence decision-making, particularly in community settings. This implies that cultural resistance can undermine the effectiveness of extension methods. A one-size-fits-all approach may not work (Van den Berg, 2004).

Table 6: Distribution of the respondents by constraints to adoption of improved rice production technologies (n=150)

Constraints to adoption of improved rice production technologies	WMS	Rank
Lack of access to information		7 th
High initial costs		6 th
Inadequate infrastructure	2.05	3 rd
Insufficient training and support		8 th
Limited access to credit		5 th
Market uncertainty		9 th

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Economic constraints	2.11	1 st
Dependency on external inputs		12 th
Variability in results		11 th
Knowledge and information gaps	2.08	2 nd
Policy and institutional barriers		13 th
Environmental factors		10 th
Cultural and social resistance	2.03	4 th

WMS-Weighted mean score

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Hypothesis testing

There is no significant relationship between the respondents’ demographic characteristics and effects of agricultural extension teaching methods on the adoption of improved rice production technologies

Relationship between respondents’ demographic characteristics and effects of agricultural extension teaching methods on the adoption of improved rice production technologies

The Correlation analysis result presented in Table 7 revealed that there exist a significant relationship between respondents’ age ($r=0.571$, $p=0.000$), household size ($r=0.549$, $p=0.000$), years spent in formal school ($r=0.532$, $p=0.000$), years of experience in rice farming ($r=0.585$, $p=0.000$), size of rice farm ($r=0.567$, $p=0.000$) and annual income ($r=0.529$, $p=0.000$) and effects of agricultural extension teaching methods on the adoption of improved rice production technologies. Younger farmers tend to be more open to adopting new technologies compared to older farmers, who may rely on traditional practices. Studies suggest that younger farmers are more inclined

to experiment with innovations due to their familiarity with technology (Rogers, 2003). Larger household sizes may correlate with a greater labour pool, enabling the adoption of labour-intensive technologies. However, this can also lead to competition for resources (Ouma, 2015). Increased educational attainment often leads to a better understanding of agricultural practices and technologies. Education equips farmers with critical thinking skills, which are essential for adopting complex farming techniques (Khan et al., 2017). Experience can be a double-edged sword; while seasoned farmers may have valuable knowledge, they may also be resistant to change. However, experienced farmers who engage with extension services can adopt innovations effectively (Ajani, 2013). Larger farms may have better access to resources and capital, facilitating the adoption of advanced technologies. In contrast, smaller farms may struggle due to limited access to credit and inputs (Birkhaeuser et al., 1991). Higher income levels can enhance farmers’ ability to invest in new technologies and inputs, thereby improving production efficiency. Conversely, low-income

farmers may lack the resources to adopt improved practices (Zhou, 2017).

Table 7: Summary of Correlation analysis showing the relationship between respondents' demographic characteristics and effects of agricultural extension teaching methods on the adoption of improved rice production technologies

Variables	r-value	p-value	Decision
Age	0.571	0.000	Significant
Household size	0.549	0.000	Significant
Number of years spent schooling	0.532	0.000	Significant
Years of experience in rice farming	0.585	0.000	Significant
Size of rice farm	0.567	0.000	Significant
Annual income	0.529	0.000	Significant

Significant at 5% level of significance

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, the findings of this study underscore the effects of agricultural extension teaching methods on the adoption of improved rice production technologies among farmers. The high level of effectiveness of these methods correlates positively with farmers' willingness and ability to embrace innovations that lead to enhanced productivity and income. Furthermore, despite the clear benefits of adopting improved technologies, several constraints such as limited access to resources, inadequate training, and socio-economic factors persist. Addressing these barriers is essential for

maximizing the potential of agricultural extension services to foster sustainable agricultural practices. It was recommended that;

1. Development of targeted training programs that cater to the specific needs of farmers, focusing on practical applications of improved rice production technologies.
2. Implementation of a mix of extension teaching methods, including hands-on demonstrations, group discussions, and digital platforms, to accommodate different learning styles and increase reach.

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3. Facilitation of better access to financial resources, seeds, and equipment necessary for adopting improved technologies, thereby reducing the economic barriers to adoption.

4. Establishment of robust feedback channels between farmers and extension agents to continuously assess the effectiveness of teaching methods and make necessary adjustments.

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5. Promotion of community-based initiatives that encourage collaborative learning and sharing of experiences among farmers, fostering a supportive network for technology adoption.

6. Advocacy for policies that provide incentives for farmers who adopt improved rice production technologies, thus encouraging wider adoption and investment in agricultural innovation.

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